

FINANCING MECHANISMS AND MACROECONOMIC OUTCOMES IN SOME SELECTED SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

With the rising access to both domestic and foreign finance, the Sub-Saharan African economies have remained concerned with the unstable growth paths and escalating debt burden. Therefore, the pivot of this research rests on analysing the synergy between financing mechanisms and macroeconomic outcomes in selected Sub-Saharan African countries. This study is a panel data analysis that involves 40 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa between 1990 and 2023. World Development Indicator (WDI) was used as secondary data source. Applying both the fixed effects and random effects regression models with additional endogeneity problem being dealt with through the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), the paper aims to recognize major determinants of the macroeconomic outcomes and the roles of the financing mechanisms. The findings disclosed that domestic resource mobilization- as proxy by tax revenue as a percentage of GDP exerts a strong positive effect on fiscal balance and investments levels. On the other hand, high reliance on external debt escalates inflation. Foreign Direct Investment has a beneficial impact on growth and capital formation, especially in the case of a country where institutional quality is greater. Such results emphasize the need to have a balanced and strategic mix of financing, which is supported by good fiscal governance. The study suggests those countries in Sub-Saharan African to focus on sustainable funding and develop their institutional framework to improve sustainable development.

Keywords: financing mechanisms, macroeconomic outcomes, domestic resource mobilization.

JEL Codes: G32, E44, B22

1. INTRODUCTION

The present position of the global economy is marked by increased gross instabilities and uncertainties. Empirical literature on this issue has widely and increasingly averred that an abysmal macroeconomic performance is a serious issue among various economies of the globe whether they are developed, developing or emerging economies. The aim of any nation is to be able to pursue favourable macroeconomic outcome in the long-run, and this emphasis is being mentioned among researchers and policymakers that there should be a strong and reliable synergy of financing mechanisms in lieu for sustainable macroeconomic performance (Yuan, 2022; Abramova, Artemenko & Krinichansky, 2022).

Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) is dogged by endemic macroeconomic problems affecting its growth and development such as low growth rate, inflationary pressure, fiscal imbalances and ineffective capital formation. In spite of the achievements obtained in improving domestic resource mobilization, external debt management, and foreign direct investment (FDI) attraction, the region is still battling with structural limitations that cannot enhance sustainable development. Although, these financing mechanisms have been studied separately in the previous research (for instance, Hujo & Bangura, 2020; Amutabi, 2023; Khalid, Su, Weiwei, Voinea & Srivastava, 2025), a significant gap in the literature exists regarding how they interact

to influence major macroeconomic variables especially growth, inflation, fiscal balance and capital formation in both the pre-COVID environment and as part of the post-pandemic economy era.

Furthermore, the current macroeconomic theories, including the Debt overhang theory, Debt sustainability models, and the FDI-led growth theories, among others, do not comprehensively explain the non-linear and context-specific relationships among deposit resource mobilization, external debt, and FDI in SSA. As an example, whereas neoclassical models imply that the growth can be financed by external borrowing, the empirical evidence in SSA reveals the debt overhang effects, meaning that high-debt levels crowd out investment (Okwoche & Makanza, 2023). Moreover, the endogenous growth theory assumes that FDI improves productivity, but in case of SSA, the poor institutional capacity tends to realize little technology transfer and crowd-out of the local firms. Also, fiscal theories suppose that deposit mobilization (e.g tax reforms) is stabilizing in terms of prices but in SSA, the incongruence of the informal sector and poor tax compliance behaviour destroys this connection. As pointed out by scholars, there is no coherent structure on how simultaneous shocks to deposit resource mobilization, debt and foreign direct investment affect the distortion of fiscal and monetary policy transmission in SSA countries.

Further, by reviewing critically the World Bank (2024) report on the economic outlook in the Sub-Saharan African setting, it can be seen that since post-2020, the SSA economies were confronted by: a slow growth in GDP, averaging 3.1 per cent in 2023, which is lower compared to the pre-pandemic times, because of commodity price volatility and global financial tightening, increasing inflation, triggered by currency depreciation, supply-chain disruptions. Also, a look at the fiscal deficits in the SSA region reveals that the median debt-to-GDP ratios have exploded to 60.1 percent in 2020, and 47 percent of the SSA countries are at a high risk of debt distress as of 2024. The gross fixed capital formation which is an index of weak capital formation stagnated at 20 percent of GDP which is far much below the 25-30 percent required in industrialization.

Besides, scholars have stated that monetary processes can greatly impact the total macroeconomic yield of a country usually quantified by the rate of growth in GDP, inflation, fiscal balance and capital formation. These processes may either increase or reduce the economic swings which may further increase business cycles and financial crises. In view of this, empirical investigations on the link between financing mechanisms through domestic resource mobilization, external debt and foreign direct investment on the macroeconomic outputs has emerged among researchers such as Abdullahi (2016); Altunyan, Kotcofana and Bazzhina (2020) among others. Therefore, understanding their interplay is essential for informed decision-making among policymakers.

Our analytic frame is new and highly different as it is guided by some major considerations: First, some major preliminary statistical features of the series are considered by examining the descriptive statistics, co-movement and linear association of the series and other features of the panel data. Such tests are a necessary beginning of specification of a model, since, fundamentally, there is no true model and that they remind us of specification bias (Aguilar, Allmaras, Bangerth & Tenorio, 2015). Second, a panel unit root test is conducted in order to check the stationarity characteristics of the series being studied. The application of panel stationarity test is quite new yet necessitated by the fact that time series properties might be identified in panel data (Karavias, Tzavalis & Zhang, 2022).

Also, the comparative advantage of the study is the adoption of the fixed effect model and the random effect models in as far as panel data analyses are concerned. The determinant of the

more appropriately suited one of the two models is made in accordance with the Hausman test as established by Pandey, Kiran and Sharma (2023). Also, in dealing with the issues of panel analyses as brought out by Felipe and Ranald (2013), this study together with the panel models adopted the system-Generalized Moment of Model (GMM) proposed by Lee and Yu (2014) to examine the relationship between financing mechanisms and macroeconomic outcomes in a sample of some countries in sub-Saharan Africa.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows: Section two delves into the review of relevant and related literature; Section three encompasses the methodology and theoretical framework. Section four discusses the empirical results and the final section concludes the study with key policy recommendations based on the results

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Literature

The theoretical postulations on the synergy between financing mechanisms and macroeconomic outcomes are under three main approaches: the Debt Overhang, the Financial Intermediation, and, the Debt sustainability models, The Debt Overhang Theory argues that when a country accumulates excessive public debt, investors expect future taxation or austerity that will reduce their returns. This discourages investment, lowers productivity, and slows economic growth. In relation to financing mechanisms, unsustainable external borrowing increases debt-servicing pressures, reduces fiscal space, and limits investment in productive sectors, thereby weakening domestic resource mobilization. High debt also undermines the benefits of FDI, as rising risk perceptions discourage capital inflows or raise the cost of investment. The Debt Sustainability Model illustrates how a country's ability to meet its debt obligations without undermining economic stability is closely tied to the way financing mechanisms are managed. When external debt, domestic revenue mobilization, and foreign direct investment are efficiently utilized, they reinforce debt sustainability, creating room for stable economic growth, sound fiscal balances, and increased investment. Conversely, excessive or poorly managed debt raises debt service costs, crowds out productive investment, fuels inflation, and strains fiscal capacity, undermining macroeconomic outcomes. The Financial Intermediation Theory shows that strong financial institutions efficiently channel domestic revenue, debt, and FDI into productive investment, promoting higher growth, stable inflation, better fiscal balance, and increased capital formation, while weak intermediation leads to resource misallocation and poor macroeconomic outcomes.

2.2. Review of Empirical Literature

The interplay between financing mechanisms and macroeconomic outcomes in selected Sub-Saharan Africa countries has been an issue of debate over time. The impacts of the available studies, to some extent, ranged from positive to negative impact.

Recently, a study was carried out by Mamuti, Kadiu, Sherifi, Romanova and Grima (2025) on financialisation and growth in emerging markets in the Croatian context for the periods 1995-2021. Time-series econometrics (ADF, johansen's co-integration, VECM and granger causality) was adopted. Findings reveal long-term equilibrium exists between financialisation and growth. The study concludes that emerging markets need tailored policies to balance financial deepening and stability.

Also, Wahyudin (2025) studied the role of monetary policy in addressing economic and financial challenges, with a focus on effective strategies for managing inflation and promoting balanced economic growth. The study used a quantitative approach through the gathering of macroeconomic data in analysis using regression techniques and economic models. Findings indicate that monetary policy, particularly in terms of adjusting interest rates and regulating the

money supply has a significant impact on controlling the inflation rate. Additionally, monetary policies aligned with the goals of sustainable economic growth are necessary to create conducive conditions for investments and consumptions.

An emerging study was carried out in the Greek context by Eftichai (2024) on the nexus between financial mechanisms and economic performance. The study seeks to investigate the impact of direct and indirect financial mechanisms on the economic performance over the period 1999-2019. Employing bivariate analysis and the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) technique, the study reveals diverse interactions among key macroeconomic factors. Direct finance, exemplified by heightened stock market activity, exhibit a positive impact on economic growth. Meanwhile, lagged inflation, indirect finance, and foreign direct investment emerge as significant contributors to inflation. The study concludes that Greece's financial mechanisms deviate from international patterns, requiring tailored policy interventions.

A study conducted by Fazaalloh (2024) examined FDI's impact on Indonesia's economic growth, using sectoral data across 33 provinces from 2010-2019. Using a Fixed Effects Model, He found out that FDI significantly promotes economic growth in Indonesian provinces. However, sector-specific analysis, particularly within agriculture, indicated that FDI exerted a notably adverse impact. Monogbe (2016) considers the period 1981-2014. Upon the use of several techniques which include OLS and Granger-causality, findings show a significantly positive relationship between external debt and growth. The paper therefore recommends that government should be meticulous about which sector of the economy funds are channeled when spending is being increased via external debt

Additionally, Emeka (2024) supported that FDI positively enhances economic growth by bolstering capital formation and enabling technology transfer. Also, Cballero, Cabalie, Caravello and Simsek (2024) investigated how financial conditions matter more than interest rates: a new framework for monetary policy. The scope of the research was to examine the role of financial conditions in macroeconomic outcomes. Structural VAR and counterfactual analysis was adopted as the method of data analysis. Empirical feedback reveals that financial conditions, not just policy rates, drive economic resilience. Also, it was revealed that stock market volatility significantly affects output gaps. The study concluded that central banks should target financial conditions indices to stabilize economies.

Contributions made by Olaoye (2023) studies the impact of government debt on macroeconomic performance and the study also examines if past relief from debt has an enhancing effect on Sub-Saharan Africa countries. The study adopted two-step system GMM, to cater for potential endogeneity and feedback effects in the dynamic panel models and also make use of the two-stage least squares (2SLS) estimation method for robustness measure. The results show that prior debt reduction initiatives had a negligibly small impact on regional economic expansion.

Finally, Adegboyega (2018) investigated the impact of external debt on economic growth between 1981 and 2016 in Nigeria. While the ARDLshort-run results establish a negative impact of exchange rate on growth, a positive effect is rather revealed specifically from the ratio of external debt to gross national income, and between ratio of reserves to total debt and foreign exchange rate. Thus, the paper recommends the use of self-liquidating investment as a panacea to long-term external debt problems. Also, Ewubare, Nteegah and Okpoi (2017) consider the period 1980-2015. The ARDL result reveals that external debt is significant and positively stimulates growth. Prudent utilization of borrowed funds, among others, is thus recommended. In review, the paper reports 'no structural break' whereas it does not account for the non-stationarity of GDPR. In addition, the long-run and short-run results fail to

show estimated values of GDP_{t-1} which is fundamentally required in the use of ARDL as a dynamic technique

Despite the extensive body of research, several gaps remain unaddressed. First, empirical studies focus on external debt as a financial mechanism while other financing mechanisms like Official Development Assistance are yet to be explored. By addressing these gaps, the current study aims to contribute a comprehensive and interdisciplinary analysis that advances the understanding of this of the economy.

3. METHODOLOGY AND MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

3.1. Theoretical Framework

The research is based on the Financial Intermediation Theory which was influenced by the prominent contribution of the work of Gurley & Shaw (1956) and Ronald McKinnon (1973). These scholars provided the starting point of how financial institutions promote the economic growth process, efficient usage and deployment of sources of finance. The theory is applicable in Sub-Saharan Africa since it highlights how powerful financial systems can change the structure of financing mechanisms (including the processes of domestic revenue mobilization, foreign direct investment, external borrowing, aid, and remittances) to positive macroeconomic results such as the growth of the economy, jobs, inflation management, and balance of the fiscal situation. Poor financial intermediation common in SSA is likely to result in resource consumption, low yields on investments and poor economic performance. Therefore, the enhancement of financial intermediaries is key in ensuring how the different sources of finance play a valuable role in the growth of sustainable macroeconomic growth within the region.

The Financing Intermediation Theory therefore connects financing mechanisms to macroeconomic performance as it focuses on the structure, efficiency and dependability of financial systems in determining how resources are converted into productive investment. It equally offers a theoretical rationale in the study of interplay between the public and private funding, debt sustainability and growth mostly in developing economies such as Nigeria where financial market imperfections play major roles.

3.2. Model specifications

The study uses a traditional methodology to harmonize the quantitative forecasting models to determine the spill-over effect between mechanisms of financing and macro-economic performance within Sub-Saharan Africa. We use a secondary data which is publicly available between 1990 to 2023 across forty (40) countries in the Sub-Saharan African region (covering nations such as Nigeria, Ghana, Egypt, Kenya, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Central African Republic, Mozambique, Niger, Rwanda, Senegal, Tanzania, Botswana, South Africa, Mali, Sudan, Sao Tome, Eritrea, Chad, Somalia, Cote D' Ivoire, Burkina Faso, and so on. The information used in the study was from the World Bank database.

The macroeconomic outcomes that are captured as the response variables are shown as Real GDP growth (RGDP), inflation (INFR), fiscal balance (FIB), and capital formation (GCFC). We also used the explanatory variables such as domestic resource mobilization (DRM), the external debt (EXD) and foreign direct investment (FDI) adopted in the study's analysis. In order to test this relationship with financing mechanisms against the macroeconomic outcomes, we have considered the Generalised Least Square (GLS) (static panel) and system-GMM estimators by Arellano and Bond (1991). The GMM is advanced and most current type of OLS and GLS estimation which is able to deal with endogeneity either through instrument variables and it is asymptotically efficient under optimal weighting (Magazzini, 2024; Liengaard, Becker, Bennedsen, Heiler, Taylor & Ringle, 2025). Sawadogo and Ouoba (2024) aver that the

system-GMM addresses the challenge of possible endogeneity that might arise due to the potential reverse causation amongst the explanatory variables and the macro-economic outputs. The system-GMM model is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 RGDP_{it} &= \delta_o + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_1 RGDP_{it-1} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_2 DRM_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_3 EXD_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_4 FDI_{it} + \mu_{it} \\
 INFR_{it} &= \delta_o + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_1 INFR_{it-1} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_2 DRM_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_3 EXD_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_4 FDI_{it} + \mu_{it} \\
 FIB_{it} &= \delta_o + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_1 FIB_{it-1} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_2 DRM_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_3 EXD_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_4 FDI_{it} + \mu_{it} \\
 GCFC_{it} &= \delta_o + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_1 GCFC_{it-1} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_2 DRM_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_3 EXD_{it} + \sum_{t=1}^k \delta_4 FDI_{it} + \mu_{it}
 \end{aligned}$$

where Growth rate of gross domestic product (GGDP), Inflation rate (INFR), Fiscal balance (FIB) and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GCFC) represent the proxy for macroeconomic outcomes in view of the fact that the study is multivariate in nature with four(4) responses variables, DRM represents the proxy for domestic resource mobilization, EXD represents external debts, FDI is a proxy for foreign direct investment, $\delta_1 - \delta_4$ represents the parameters, it represents the panel (time periods and cross-section), and U represents the disturbance term. Theoretically, $\delta_2 - \delta_4 > 0$ (see Table 1).

Table 1: Data, Measurements, Description, and literature justification of the Variables

Symbol	Definition	Variables	Measurement	Literature Justification	Expected Signs
RGDP	Real GDP Growth	DV	Measured as the annualized GDP growth rate within the observed years in SSA countries	Eftichai (2024)	N/A
INFR	Inflation rate	DV	Calculated as the consumer price index within the observed years in SSA countries	Wahyudin (2025)	N/A
FIB	Fiscal balance	DV	Measured as debt-GDP ratio	IMF Fiscal Monitor	N/A
GCFC	Capital formation	DV	Measured as gross investment	IMF Fiscal Monitor	N/A
DRM	Domestic Resource Mobilization	IV	Calculated as tax revenue as a percentage of GDP	Cabaliero, Caravello and Simsek (2024)	+(-)
EXD	External debt	IV	Measured as the total foreign debts within the observed years of consideration.	Olaoye (2023)	+(-)
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment	IV	Calculated as annual levels of investment within the selected countries	Eftichai (2024)	+(-)

Source: Authors' compilation from available Literature, 2025.

4. Results and Discussion

The study's analytical findings provide a thorough illustration of how macroeconomic outcomes and financing mechanisms are intertwined in the context of Sub-Saharan Africa.

4.1. Descriptive Analysis

Table 2 shows the preliminary findings (descriptive statistical values) of the variables in the intervals of 1990-2023. Representing in the Table 2 below, the average growth rate of GDP (RGDP) shows value of 6.54 where Ghana (0.13) and Mali (17.39) have the lowest and highest values in 2005 and 2022 respectively. This consequently concludes that GDP growth is beyond the long run levels of Mali which might have indicated that it might be undergoing boom or overheating of the economy. The low values of 6 % in SSA were an indicator that majority of SSA countries are undergoing volatility in growth. Observing that, the highest value of GDP growths is 15.18 meaning that SSAs growth potential is underestimated in case it is sustainable. Moreover, there is a significant fluctuation in the domestic resource mobilization expressed as tax revenues in the sample. The highest figure of 8.43 percent is within the domestic resource mobilization which indicates weal revenue that is common in the fragile SSA regions. The area should aim at expanding their tax base with the virtual collection of revenues.

Table 2: Summary Statistics

	Obs	Std. Dev.	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
RGDP	710	2.99	6.54	6.00	15.18
INFR	710	4.25	4.11	3.23	10.21
FIB	710	6.11	7.10	3.04	9.38
GCFC	710	1.59	2.17	5.13	11.22
DRM	710	4.66	10.83	4.77	8.43
EXD	710	2.18	5.10	10.54	14.36
FDI	710	2.33	19.97	11.04	22.18

Source: Output of summary statistics obtained from E-views 12, 2025

4.2. Correlation Matrix

Table 3 indicates the correlation matrix which reflects the pair correlation coefficient (r) among the variables. It finds out the direction and the strength of relationship between the variables. The growth rate of gross domestic product and deposit resource mobilization depicts positive correlation (0.542) as expected; indicating that the higher mobilization of deposit resource in the financial system is connected with a higher GDP growth. This is in line with economic theory because the enhanced mobilization of financial resources is supportive of investments, extended credits and improved economy. As well, the low positive value of its coefficient (0.205) of external debt demonstrates that it bears a very weak linear and direct correlation with the growth of GDP. This is possibly because the debt can be used to finance positive investment, but borrowing of funds in excess in an economy will mean payment without the anticipated growth outcome. There is positive relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and growth in GDP that indicates that increase in GDP is associated with foreign direct investment in terms of injecting capital, technology and creating employment.

In addition to that, the Table 3 below shows correlation between inflation and the explanatory variables. There was negative relationship between deposit resource mobilization and inflation that implies that there can be stabilization of money supply by increasing savings and credit availability and stabilizing supply-pull inflation. Also external debt coefficient value of 0.361 depicts that the higher the external debt the higher the inflation. A more in-depth explanation

would imply that a high debt would depreciate the currency thus increasing the cost of imported goods (cost-push inflation). The outcome also indicates that FDI does not have any linear relationship with GDP growth whose coefficient value is 0.07. It can be reasoned that inflow of FDI in the SSA region can improve the productivity (supply side effect) so this can negate pressure of inflation.

Furthermore, Table 3 below depicted the correlation which co-exist between the dependent variable, fiscal balance and the three independent variables. Deposit resource mobilization (0.140), external debt (0.258) and foreign direct investment (0.383). Given this affiliation, increased mobilization of the resource of deposits is likely to increase government revenue in minor ways. Besides, revenue generating projects within SSA regions may be financed through borrowed money. Also, FDI increases economic activity that increases tax revenues without any explicit expenditures on the part of the authorities.

Lastly, the correlation between gross fixed capital formation and the explanatory variables for this study is shown in Table 3 below. They all reported a positive nexus. Going by the analysis of the correlation matrix, it can be concluded that the possibility of multi-collinearity issue do not arise in the study model between the values are between 0.000 to 0.542 which is far below the thresholds as established by Kim (2019) who averred that high values of correlation matrix will lead to multi-collinearity problems and misleading statistical results..

Table 3: Matrix of Correlation

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
RGDP	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-
INFR	1.000	1.000	-	-	-	-	-
FIB	1.000	1.000	1.000	-	-	-	-
GCFC	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	-	-	-
DRM	0.542	-0.321	0.140	0.418	1.000	-	-
EXD	0.205	0.361	0.258	0.285	0.392	1.000	-
FDI	0.350	0.07	0.383	0.376	-0.319	0.06	1.000

Source: Output of summary statistics obtained from E-views 12, 2025

4.3 Panel unit root test

The unit root test is required to ascertain the order of integration of the series and to choose the best approach to use in this investigation. The study conducted the Levin-Lin, and Chu (LLC) panel unit because it assumes cross-sectional independence across the model. The unit root is necessary because one of the assumptions of GMM estimator about data is that of stationarity, which is crucial for meaningful interpretation of the GMM results. Table 4 displays the panel unit root. The results are consistent with an inference that the series are integrated of order one I(1). This does not only rule out the likelihood of spuriousness of the estimation output, it also provides a justification for the use system-GMM which tolerates series with the found order of integration.

Table 4: Unit Root Result			
	Level	First Diff.	Order of integration
RGDP	2.138	-4.543*	(1)
INFR	2.004	-3.471*	(1)
FIB	2.492	-4.112*	(1)
GCFC	3.129.	-3.753*	(1)

DRM	1.452	-2.921*	(1)
EXD	1.885	-3.339*	(1)
FDI	3.214	-4.816*	(1)
<i>Note: * represent P-value at 5% level.</i>			
Source: Authors' computation from E -views, 2025			

Table 5: Panel Co-integration

Variables	Panel Cointegration	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Integration
		1	2	3	[4	
Westerlund panel-data cointegration test						
RGDP	Group-mean variance-ratio (VR) statistic	-0.668	0.251	-0.538	0.295	No
	Panel VR statistic	-0.191	0.424	-0.949	0.171	No
INFR	Group-mean variance-ratio (VR) statistic	1.466*	0.071	1.733*	0.041	Yes
	Panel VR statistic	-0.001	0.499	-0.389	0.348	Yes
FIB	Group-mean variance-ratio (VR) statistic	1.688*	0.045	1.182	0.119	Yes
	Panel VR statistic	0.236	0.406	-0.075	0.469	Yes
GCFC	Group-mean variance-ratio (VR) statistic	2.208*	0.434	0.809	0.209*	Yes
	Panel VR statistic	-0.355	0.361	0.719	0.236	Yes
DRM	Group-mean variance-ratio (VR) statistic	0.165	0.434	0.809	0.209	No
	Panel VR statistic	-0.355	0.361	0.719	0.236	No
EXD	Group-mean variance-ratio (VR) statistic	2.511	0.006	0.964	0.167	No
	Panel VR statistic	0.428	0.334	0.809	0.209	No
FDI	Group-mean variance-ratio (VR) statistic	0.236*	0.406	-0.007	0.469*	Yes
	Panel VR statistic	-0.143	0.443	-0.617	0.268	Yes
<i>Note: * represent Pvalue at 5% level. [1], [2], [3] and [4] represent equations with RGDP, INFR, FIB and GCFC as dependent variables, respectively.</i>						

Source: Authors' computation from E-views, 2025

After testing for the stationarity of the variables at their first difference, the subsequent estimation is to confirm whether there is existence of long-run relationship. In view of that, this, study employs the Westerlund panel-data cointegration test and the result is presented in Table 5. Moreover, Table 5 shows four different estimations, of which [1] represents equation (1) in section 3, [2] represents equation (2) in section 3, [3] represents equation (3) in section

3 and [4] represents equation (4) in section 3. Given the H_0 of no cointegration, Westerlund panel-data cointegration test exhibits rejection of the H_0 for model 1,2, 3 and 4. In all, there exists four co-integration among the variables.

Table.6: Two- step system GMM Results

Variables	Model 1 RGDP	Model 2 INFR	Model 3 FIB	Model 4 GCFC
DRM	1.59 [0.24]	-1.56* [3.66]	6.15* [4.32]	1.96* [3.49]
EXD	-3.68 [1.19]	-1.98 [0.74]	-4.59 [2.60]	-2.11 [4.10]
FDI	7.93* [4.60]	4.61* [3.60]	2.65 [4.22]	1.58* [2.27]
R-Squared	0.741	0.557	0.672	0.486
Adjusted R-Squared	0.726	0.536	0.624	0.461
No. of Observation	510	510	510	510
No of countries	40	40	40	40
<i>Note: * represent Pvalue at 5% level in model [1], [2], [3] and [4] represents equations stated as dependent variables, respectively. [] represents the T-statistics.</i>				

Source: Output of summary statistics obtained from E-views, 2025

Based on Table 6, in Model 1 of the GMM regression estimations, the coefficient value will be 1.59 which implies that when the domestic resource mobilization level (that is, the tax revenue/GDP) increases by one unit, the growth rate of the GDP increases by 1.59 units, other things being kept constant (ceteris paribus). The fact that there is a positive coefficient suggests that increasing tax revenue (as a proxy of domestic mobilization) has been a possible source of economic growth perhaps by such means as increasing government spending on infrastructure, public services or investment incentives. Nonetheless, the result of the empirical feedback places the relationship as insignificant. The result has an input into the bigger discussion of financial intermediation and macroeconomic outcomes. Our empirical evidence did not confirm some of the theoretically-based hypotheses of the relationship between domestic resource mobilization and GDP growth rate. Our results have evidence that cannot back up the results of Eftichai (2024) in assigning a positive and significant relationship between domestic resource mobilization and GDP growth rate, this may be due to weak institutions in Sub-Saharan African countries

Besides, the finding indicates that the relationship between external debt and macroeconomic outcome in terms of the growth rate of GDP is negative and insignificant may be due to mismanagement of borrowed funds. The conclusion that the external debt has negative impacts on the economy contradicts what Olaoye (2023) has found that external debt boosts the economy. In addition, the finding shows that foreign direct investments are positively and significantly correlated with macroeconomic output. This comes along with the existing theoretical findings that high and strong foreign direct investment influence macroeconomic outcomes.

Relatively to model 2, Table 6 indicates that macroeconomic outcomes in the form of the inflation rate are significantly (P-value<0.05) explained by Domestic resource mobilization (1.56) and foreign direct investment (4.61). Nevertheless, the external debts show the reverse correlation (-1.96). This observation of negative coefficient of domestic resource mobilization on inflation implies that increase in government revenue (i.e. taxes) can decrease the

dependency on borrowing. Demand-pull inflation might also be alleviated by mobilization of domestic savings to finance productive capacity. In addition, the positive coefficient of foreign direct investments on inflation shows that increased flow of FDI relates to increases in inflation. This result is in line with a study such as Eftichai (2024) that provided an important relationship. Nevertheless, the direct effect of external debt on inflation rate implies that, high external debt SSA governments can print money to liquidate their debts and this enhances inflation.

Further, this relationship in model 3, shows one unit change in the domestic resource mobilization (i.e. tax revenue) translates into a 6.15 unit improvement in fiscal balance. This goes hand in hand with economic theory that an increased amount of taxes collected will decrease the dependency on borrowing thus enhancing the budgetary health. Also one finds in table 6 a positive relationship between an indirect coefficients of external debts to fiscal balance consistent with the economic theory of showing that the costs involved in servicing the debts could cause strain on government budgets and that the flooding in debts could even be an observation of weaknesses in the fiscal matters.

In addition, according to model 4, the findings indicate that domestic resource mobilization (1.96) was significant ($P\text{-value} < 0.05$) in explaining investment indicating that as a result of increased domestic resources (tax revenues), a greater investment is possible and fiscal space is created to allow the government to invest. This is also an indication of macroeconomic stability to the private investors. The outcome however indicates that the effect of external debt on gross fixed capital formation is negative and insignificant, hence, indicates a lower level of investment. This can be attributed to debt overhang effect that presupposes high debt discourages investment. It is also unveiled that FDI is a good capital formative driver, which implies favorable spillovers besides direct investment.

DRM does not significantly influence economic growth in Model 1 because its p-value of 0.24 is higher than the 0.05 threshold, meaning its positive coefficient cannot be considered statistically meaningful. In contrast, DRM is statistically significant in both the inflation and fiscal balance models, with p-values of 3.66 and 4.32, which fall below the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that DRM exerts a real and measurable effect in those models, specifically, it helps reduce inflation and strengthens fiscal balance.

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

In the current research, a chain of econometric methods have been utilized to analyze the response of financing mechanisms and macroeconomic outcomes with a particular concern on 40 SSA countries extending over the years 1990 to 2023. The findings indicate that domestic resource mobilization- proxied by tax revenue as a percentage of GDP has a high positive effect on fiscal balance and the investment level. On the contrary, over-reliance on international borrowing enhances inflation pressure and macro-economic instability. The concept of foreign direct investment is seen to have a positive impact on growth and capital formation especially when the institution is stronger in an economy. The following recommendations were given based on the results.

First and foremost, these results reinforce the necessity of optimal financing mix that is based on good fiscal governance, and institutional reforms. This study suggests that Sub-Saharan African states should accelerate their domestic revenue mobilization in a sustainable way, upgrading debt management system, and intensify the institutional framework in boosting favorable macroeconomic performance and sustainable development

Increase capital formation by channeling public expenditure toward infrastructure, technology, and private-sector-driven investment. Capital formation increases when government spending is directed toward projects that expand the economy's productive capacity. Prioritizing infrastructure such as power, transport, and digital connectivity, lowers production costs and attracts private investment. Supporting technology adoption and innovation improves productivity across sectors. Public funds can also be used to leverage private-sector investment through public-private partnerships, targeted incentives, and credit guarantees. This approach not only stimulates immediate investment but also drives long-term growth by enhancing competitiveness and expanding productive assets.

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